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D3.8 – Consumer engagement and design validation roadmap v2

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A key part of the ACCEPT project is developing tools and services *with* energy communities, as opposed to *for* energy communities. To ensure this user-centred approach is taken for the development of these tools and services, it is essential to have a comprehensive consumer engagement and design validation roadmap.

By implementing a well-defined methodology and considering the engagement activities required for consumers and prosumers as well as activities for validating the ACCEPT tools and services a comprehensive consumer engagement and design validation roadmap has been defined.

The generation of the engagement and design validation roadmap was reliant on the implementation of a new methodology. In the previous methodology outlined in D3.7, the pilot-specific engagement roadmaps would be defined following remote-based workshops and interviews with pilot partners and pilot community members. However, without undertaking an in-person site visit, as opposed to a remote-based methodology, first-hand community research and face-to-face interactions with the community, the information gathered for developing a pilot-specific engagement plan was deemed sub-optimal. Therefore, the methodology for planning the pilot-specific engagement roadmaps was delayed to ensure information from the in-person site visit could be incorporated into the planning. Currently, 3 of the 4 in-person site visits have been completed, with the final site visit scheduled for the end of M23 (November 2022). Following the completion of the site visits, checkpoint meetings with each pilot site leader are planned for M26 in which the pilot-specific engagement roadmaps will be defined.

The consumer engagement and design validation roadmap is comprised of two main elements, **consumer engagement**, which focuses on the needs of pilot site communities, citizens and stakeholders and **design validation**, which focuses on gathering feedback on the ACCEPT project solutions and services, such as persona development, user testing or business model assessment.

With regards to the **consumer engagement** element, to ensure the required activities are included which accommodate the unique community needs within each pilot region. To this end, the site visits currently being conducted provided an opportunity to gather information to build an understanding of the environment, culture and society and interact with community members in each pilot region. The insights from the observations of the site visits and the information and feedback gathered for the community interactions were analysed through a Barriers, Needs and Opportunities model to identify key topics of interest which are vital for the planning of a pilot-specific engagement roadmap.

Regarding the **design validation** element, two key engagement activity plans have been defined related to the tools and services, persona development and C-APP user testing. The persona development research allows for the identification of profiles based on real users within a community. A clear plan for the personas is defined, detailing each required step from the questionnaire design, to the analysis and finalisation of persona profiles which can be validated and used as a guide for developers of the C-APP. Concerning the technical development of the C-APP, a framework for the development of the C-APP which includes internal (project partners) and external (community end users) assessment is provided. A process is defined for the planning of the external user testing which includes a step-by-step explanation and timeline for defining the goals of the session, preparing the required materials, and conducting training sessions with pilot partners so they are prepared to carry out user testing with the community members, executing the user testing sessions and analysing the feedback generated.

TABLE OF CONTENT

- 1. Introduction 7**
 - 1.1. *Scope and objectives of task* 7
 - 1.2. *Structure of deliverable*..... 7
 - 1.3. *Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables*..... 7
- 2. Consumer engagement and design validation roadmap 8**
 - 2.1. *Roadmap*..... 8
 - 2.2. *Next steps* 10
- 3. Consumer engagement 11**
 - 3.1. *Methodology*..... 11
 - 3.2. *Pilot site visits* 12
 - 3.2.1. *Analysis*..... 12
- 4. Design validation 26**
 - 4.1. *Persona development* 26
 - 4.1.3. *Analysis*..... 28
 - 4.2. *User testing roadmap* 30
- 5. Conclusion 33**
- 6. References 34**
- 7. Appendix 35**
 - 7.1. *Appendix A: Persona development questionnaire* 35
 - 7.2. *Appendix B: User testing consent form*..... 40
 - 7.3. *Appendix C: User testing briefing document*..... 41
 - 7.4. *Appendix D: User testing guidance notes* 42
 - 7.5. *Appendix E: User testing discussion guide*..... 43
 - 7.6. *Appendix F: System Usability Scale*..... 45

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Methodology for developing pilot-specific engagement roadmap.....	10
Figure 2. Updated methodology for developing pilot-specific engagement roadmaps.....	11
Figure 3. Barriers, Needs and Opportunities model.....	13
Figure 4. WP3 leaders and pilot partners interviewing a local energy expert	14
Figure 5. Focus group with citizens from the Santomera region.....	14
Figure 6. Focus group with citizens from the Murcia region	14
Figure 7. Dutch pilot partners giving a guided tour to WP3 leaders	17
Figure 8. ACCEPT presentation given by Dutch pilot partners and WP3 leaders.....	18
Figure 9. Swiss pilot partners providing WP3 with a tour of the pilot region.....	21
Figure 10. Example of a persona profile	28
Figure 11. Persona development timeline	29
Figure 12. Citizen APP development methodology	30
Figure 13. External user testing planning timeline	31

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Consumer engagement and design validation roadmap.....	8
Table 2. BNO analysis of the Spanish pilot site.....	15
Table 3. BNO analysis of the Dutch pilot sit	19
Table 4. The output of the motivation assessment workshop with the Dutch pilot community	20
Table 5. BNO analysis of the Swiss pilot sit.....	22
Table 6. BNO analysis of the Greek pilot sit	25
Table 7. Questions and corresponding categories used for the quantitative section of the persona development questionnaire	27

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and objectives of task

This deliverable will describe the methods and activities which contribute to the planning of the consumer engagement and design validation roadmap for interacting with the community and relevant stakeholders in each pilot region. In addition, the methodology for planning the required engagements will be updated following the experience and knowledge gained in the project since the first version of this deliverable was submitted in M10. The objective of outlining a strategy and roadmap for the required engagements is to maximise participation in demand response schemes and uptake of the ACCEPT services and solutions.

1.2. Structure of deliverable

Chapter 2 will provide the ACCEPT consumer engagement and design validation roadmap

Chapter 3 will describe the consumer engagement methodology and present the results from the pilot site visits

Chapter 4 will describe the design validation process, including the methodology and status for the user testing of the citizen-APP (C-APP) and the persona development.

Chapter 5 will summarise and evaluate the progress thus far

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

The consumer engagement and design validation roadmap is closely related to the living lab activities (WP3: T3.1) and related deliverables (D3.1 and D3.2). The engagements described here will also be linked to the user testing and persona validation activities (WP7: T7.1). The plan for these engagement activities is explained in this deliverable, and the results and feedback gathered from the engagements will be described in deliverables D3.3 and D7.2.

2. Consumer engagement and design validation roadmap

2.1. Roadmap

The engagement activities that have been completed or planned thus far can be considered as part of a common consumer engagement and design validation roadmap for all pilot regions. This roadmap is detailed in Table 1. This roadmap covers many activities, across several WPs within the ACCEPT project which cover consumer engagement, technical development, impact assessment and business modelling and communication. Despite the comprehensive nature of this roadmap, the project and pilot communities are dynamic and the roadmap should remain flexible to accommodate changing and developing plans across work packages.

As shown in Table 1, in the current roadmap, the activities are truncated around M21-26. This is a result of the dynamic nature of engagement planning. Concrete activities are predominantly planned only a few months before being carried out. Despite only being able to concretely define activities a few months in advance, further future engagements are also included in the roadmap to provide a global outlook of the engagement roadmap. Having a broad perspective allows for appropriate adjustments, for example, if there is too much time lapse between communication activities to preserve interest or potential engagements are too close together creating logistical problems.

Table 1. Consumer engagement and design validation roadmap

Date	Activity	Description	Related WP	Status
M21	Persona development questionnaire design	To generate persona profiles, a carefully designed questionnaire which investigates specific, relevant factors was created	WP7	Complete
M21	Spanish pilot site visit	Conducting community research and observation as well as interactions with local citizens and stakeholders	WP3	Complete
M22	Persona development questionnaire distribution	The persona questionnaire was distributed amongst each pilot community	WP7	Complete
M21	C-APP external user testing partner training	Demonstrations from the technical team on how to use the C-APP and training on how to run a user testing session from WP3 leaders were given to pilot partners.	WP5, 7	
M22	Dutch pilot site visit	Conducting community research and observation as well as interactions with local citizens and stakeholders	WP3	Complete
M22	Swiss pilot site visit	Conducting community research and observation as well as interactions with local citizens and stakeholders	WP3	Complete
M23	C-APP external user testing session: Round 1	Pilot partners carry out user testing sessions with end users within their pilot community	WP5, 7	In progress
M23	Technical installation	Installation of technical devices in ACCEPT participant's residencies	WP4, 5, 7	In progress
M23	Greek pilot site visit	Conducting community research and observation as well as interactions with local citizens and stakeholders	WP3	Planned

M24	Project newsletter	Newsletter communicating highlights and key exploitable results from the project	WP9	Planned
M24	Persona development analysis	Analysis of the data gathered from the persona development questionnaires to identify user profiles	WP7	Planned
M24	C-APP external user feedback analysis	Analysis of the feedback gathered from external user testing sessions to generate recommendations for modifications to suit user needs	WP5, 7	Planned
M24	ACCEPT Information campaign	Broad dissemination activities to promote awareness of ACCEPT	WP9	Planned
M25	ACCEPT project explanation video	Creation of a video which explains what the ACCEPT project is and why it is important	WP9	Planned
M25	Final persona creation	Following the analysis, specific persona profiles will be created which can guide the development of the C-APP	WP7	Planned
M26	Checkpoint meeting with pilot partners	A key meeting between pilot partners and WP3 leaders to determine the pilot-specific engagements in the engagement roadmap	WP3, 7	Planned
M26	C-APP sharing results of feedback	Communicating with the pilot communities on how their feedback assisted the development of the C-APP	WP3, 5, 7	TBD
M27	Expert feedback on preliminary business models	Interviews with energy system experts to discuss potential business models generated in ACCEPT	WP8	TBD
M28	Persona validation activity	Holding a workshop with pilot communities to validate the personas developed	WP7	TBD
M29	C-APP external user testing session: Round 2	Pilot partners carry out the second round of user testing sessions with end users within their pilot community	WP5, 7	TBD
M30	Project Newsletter	Newsletter communicating highlights and key exploitable results from the project	WP9	TBD
M30	Pilot-specific engagement*	TBD	WP3, 7	TBD
M31	C-APP sharing results of feedback	Communicating with the pilot communities on how their feedback assisted the development of the C-APP	WP5, 7	
M33	Pilot-specific engagement*	TBD	WP3, 7	TBD
M35	Consortium evaluation workshop	A workshop with all pilot partners to evaluate the success of the ACCEPT approach and the engagement activities undertaken	WP8	TBD
M36	Project Newsletter	Newsletter communicating highlights and key exploitable results from the project	WP9	TBD
M38	Pilot-specific engagement*	TBD	WP3, 7	TBD

M39	External evaluation workshop	A workshop with citizens and stakeholders from pilot communities to evaluate the success of the ACCEPT approach and the engagement activities undertaken	WP8	TBD
M42	Project Newsletter	Newsletter communicating highlights and key exploitable results from the project	WP9	TBD

2.2. Next steps

Now a general comprehensive consumer engagement and design validation roadmap for the ACCEPT project has been created, the next step is to layer in the pilot-specific engagements. The primary method to create the pilot-specific element is through checkpoint meetings which will be held in M26 with pilot partners from each pilot site. The checkpoint meeting is an opportunity to review the general roadmap shown in Table 1 and discuss revisions such as which activities are required across all areas (communication, user testing, gathering business model feedback, etc.) and when they should take place. The foundations for this meeting will come primarily from the information and feedback gathered from the in-person pilot site visits undertaken during M21-23 (explained in chapter 3.2). The information from the observations and stakeholder meetings during the site visit provide areas of interest to focus on which guide what type of pilot-specific activity may be required to facilitate citizen engagement in the ACCEPT project. In addition to the in-person pilot site visit, information from the persona development and user testing activities (explained in chapter 4) will also be required for the checkpoint meeting for producing the pilot-specific engagement roadmaps, see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Methodology for developing pilot-specific engagement roadmap

3. Consumer engagement

The consumer engagement and design validation roadmap is comprised of two main elements, **consumer engagement**, which focuses on the needs of pilot site communities, citizens and stakeholders and **design validation**, which focuses on gathering feedback on the ACCEPT solutions and services, such as persona development and user testing. This chapter will describe the **consumer engagement** element, including an update on the methodology used, results from the pilot site visits and an explanation of the analysis used to assess each community to determine their engagement needs.

3.1. Methodology

A methodology for creating the consumer engagement and design validation roadmap was presented in the previous version of this deliverable (D3.7). The previous methodology consisted of three steps, (1) defining the objectives of the community, (2) mapping the stakeholder community and (3) determining pilot-specific engagement recommendations from the information gathered in steps 1 and 2. The gathering of information in steps 1 and 2 was done through remote interviews and workshops with the pilot partners. This was an adjustment to the plan described at the proposal stage where in-person site visits were planned for each pilot site within the first year to facilitate the generation of an engagement roadmap. However, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, travel was largely restricted which meant site visits were unable to be conducted until M21 (September 2022) of the project.

Because in-person site visits were not possible, the approach was switched to a remote-based method for understanding the pilot communities. The remote-based approach included online calls, interviews and workshops with the pilot representatives between M3-8 of the project. The goal of these online interactions was for WP3 leaders to understand each pilot community’s environment, map out key local stakeholders and the goals of the community and pilot partners for participating in ACCEPT (see deliverable D3.7 for more information on the process and results of the remote-based approach). However, difficulties were encountered when trying to outline a potential pilot-specific engagement roadmap based solely on remote-based interviews and workshops. The remote-based approach was sub-optimal as WP3 leaders, who are responsible for developing the engagement roadmap, were unable to generate a clear and comprehensive understanding of the pilot site communities, culture, society and environment that would be sufficient for suggesting effective engagement activities. The remote-based approach also removed the opportunity for face-to-face interactions with the pilot leaders or community members. Subsequently, problems were faced with regard to aligning WP3 understanding with the needs of the pilot site and project goals. Therefore, an updated methodology, shown in Figure 2, has been developed.

Figure 2. Updated methodology for developing pilot-specific engagement roadmaps

The updated methodology consists of three stages:

- **The community and pilot site understanding development** represents the gathering of information for a more detailed understanding of the pilot site ascertained from the in-person site visit.
- **The holistic community analysis and plan** stage is the assessment of the information obtained from the pilot site visits to identify key focus areas to develop targeted engagements for each pilot site.
- **The targeted engagement activity recommendations** will bring together learnings from the site visit and other engagement-related activities (persona development and user testing, etc.) pilot-specific engagement activities can be added to the engagement roadmap.

Currently, the project is in the first stage of the methodology shown in Figure 2. At the time of writing, the pilot site visits for Spain, Switzerland and the Netherlands have been completed. The Greek pilot site visit is scheduled for M23. The holistic community analysis and plan will be finalised in M24. Potential targeted engagement activity recommendations will have been created by M25 and will be discussed and finalised through the checkpoint meetings with the pilot partners in M26.

3.2. Pilot site visits

The pilot site visits are a key component of the consumer engagement and design validation roadmap. Although the primary purpose of this deliverable is to report on the plan of activities, because the site visits are integral for the planning of the pilot-specific engagement roadmaps, the results from the site visits of each pilot region will be reported here. The site visits consist of a physical site visit by the leaders of WP3 to each pilot region to make observations and develop an understanding of the community, environment, culture and facilities and services. This is complimented with activities with various stakeholders and citizens within the community, such as interviews, focus groups and workshops to gather their perspectives and insight into topics such as the energy system, sustainability and demand response. Outside energy topics, research was also undertaken to understand the social and psychological barriers and motivations that they experience within their community and daily life. Information gathered from the pilot site visits is then analysed to understand the best approach for engaging the community and determining what motivations and opportunities can be leveraged to maximise engagement. This sub-chapter will first describe how we analyse information gathered during the pilot site visits and then provide the output from this analysis for each pilot site.

3.2.1. Analysis

The results of the site visits are analysed via a Barriers, Needs and Opportunities (BNO) model, see Figure 3. The BNO model is a modified version of the Needs Opportunities and Abilities model (see Vlek, Jager & Steg, 1997; Vlek, 2000). The BNO model places a greater emphasis on analysing the perceived barriers from the community, which is a key component to address when attempting to encourage citizen engagement in sustainability projects such as ACCEPT. The BNO model allows for the information collected in the site visits via interviews, workshops and focus groups to be analysed and deconstructed into key areas to focus on for developing the pilot-specific engagement activities (represented by the change triggers and outcome stages in Figure 3). Rooting engagement activities in societal constructs determined from the BNO analysis allows activities to be created that tap into the pulse of society and elicit real change.

Figure 3. Barriers, Needs and Opportunities model

3.2.2. Pilot Site Community: Renewable Energy Cooperative Buildings, Spain

The Spanish pilot site visit was completed over 2 days in M21. An agenda for the visit was created after several online discussions between WP3 leaders and the Spanish pilot partners. The agenda included visiting the Santomera and Murcia pilot regions. In addition to the site visits, various interactions with stakeholders were organised by the pilot partners. Pilot partners were asked to try to select a variety of stakeholders, some with knowledge of the energy market/system and less knowledgeable citizens. The activities undertaken included an interview with an energy expert who was a chief engineer of efficiency services and an advisor in renewable energy communities, a focus group with 5 citizens from Santomera which included end users and prosumers, and a second focus group with 5 citizens from Murcia who were also end users and prosumers. For the interview and focus group activities, general discussion guides were created by WP3 leaders which aimed to address a variety of topics related to energy and energy communities, such as how energy is perceived, what are the main barriers to green energy behaviours and motivation towards demand response. The interview and focus group sessions were led by the pilot partners with the support of WP3 leaders. This was done so that the sessions could be in the local language to ensure participants could express themselves comfortably. The results of the BNO analysis are displayed in Table 2.

Based on the BNO analysis, the key focus areas which will be discussed with the Spanish pilot leaders in the checkpoint meeting include:

- The societal appeal of green energy and interest amongst citizens
- Opportunities for collaboration with local experts within the community
- The growing interest in PV panels
- Clarity of benefits of ACCEPT to the community (managing energy, short and long-term benefits)
- The problems of legislation and bureaucracy
- Climate change being a primary driver, monetary benefits are secondary
- Interest and curiosity promote a need for information flow
- Difference of opinion regarding Demand Response (control vs automation)
- The current cost increase of energy as a catalyst for change

Figure 4. WP3 leaders and pilot partners interviewing a local energy expert

Figure 5. Focus group with citizens from the Santomera region

Figure 6. Focus group with citizens from the Murcia region

Table 2. BNO analysis of the Spanish pilot site

Societal Context			
<p>The lack of dynamic tariffs is problematic for creating incentives related to DR for consumers. The Spanish market is divided into 2, regulated (dynamic rates set at market + retailer charge) and free (retailer and client agreement at fixed rate)</p> <p>Transfer of regulated to the free market has doubled in 2021 – mainly due to the cost of the regulated market</p> <p>PV plant installation on the rise</p> <p>Energy and the energy market should be viewed in terms of - Energy as a right, Decentralized, and include citizen ownership.</p>			
	Energy expert	Focus group 1	Focus group 2
<u>Barriers</u>	<p>Regulatory barriers for self-consumption – e.g. have to be within 500m of plant</p> <p>Energy communities are not legal figures, they must be either an energy Cooperation or an Association.</p> <p>Legal-technical: although the electrical infrastructure is ready, the technical regulation doesn't allow implementation in a wider collective self-consumption.</p> <p>Bureaucracy is a long process, DSOs delay the connection of the plants and the government tend to reject sustainability projects.</p> <p>Feeling of frustration when wanting to install PV as legislation is a huge barrier.</p>	<p>Some are concerned that ACCEPT only brings long-term benefits – would need some short-term benefits.</p> <p>Legislation is a major barrier – bureaucracy is the issue, takes too long and delays occur in installation and receiving funds.</p>	<p>Expressed concern and pessimism about current energy use, globally speaking.</p> <p>Lack of appreciation in society for how high energy use is at individual and also public levels (e.g. Christmas lights).</p> <p>Money is helping to promote sustainability but money alone is not enough to change the mentality towards energy use.</p>
<u>Needs</u>	<p>Energy communities need a management platform like what is being developed in ACCESS.</p> <p>Promoting a model where energy savings are used to fight energy poverty – those in poverty can then be part of an innovative scheme as opposed to the potential embarrassment of welfare (e.g. food banks)</p>	<p>Want to know broader information on their energy consumption – this would perhaps encourage greener energy behaviour.</p> <p>Value the economic savings but this isn't the primary reason, more concerned with the positive impact of climate change & fighting energy poverty</p>	<p>Some prefer automation and some prefer more control regarding DR.</p>

	CONSUMER ENGAGEMENT AND DESIGN VALIDATION ROADMAP	The project should have wider ambitions and include better insulation and Smart appliances	
<p><u>Opportunities</u></p>	<p>Self-consumption is on the rise and more plausible compared to pre-2019</p> <p>Crisis into opportunity, rising energy prices have led to more interest in PV installation</p> <p>Energy and the energy market should be viewed in terms - Energy as a right, Decentralized, and citizen ownership.</p> <p>The perception of PV has evolved mainly in the last few years from a lack of belief in the usefulness</p>	<p>Need to know the explicit benefits that the project brings to them</p> <p>They receive interest from neighbours towards PV panels</p>	<p>society is pushing for a change in the way we consume, at the individual and also at the collective level</p> <p>Pioneers within the community</p> <p>Info on energy use provided by ACCEPT services would be useful for consumers to understand and potentially change energy use behaviour</p> <p>utilising cost rise at the moment as the economic incentives are a major driver for interest in PV and renewable energy</p> <p>Societal discussion with neighbours, friends etc. about being part of an energy community, reducing consumption and installing PV</p> <p>Interested in providing feedback to develop ACCEPT services</p>

3.2.3. Pilot Site Community: Eva Lanxmeer Community, Netherlands

The Dutch pilot site visit was completed over 2 days in M22. An agenda for the visit was created after several online discussions between WP3 leaders and the Dutch pilot partners. The agenda included visiting the pilot region and the district assets. A project kick-off meeting was organised with 20 participants from the pilot region. In this meeting, a presentation was held in which pilot representatives explained various topics of the ACCEPT project, including the goals of the project, the partners involved, the timeline and upcoming engagements, such as the citizen APP development and installation of technological equipment. The presentation also provided an opportunity for WP3 leaders to present information regarding the persona development (explained in chapter 4), such as its goals, the process and how the citizens contribute to and from the persona development process. Due to a large number of citizen participants attending the presentation and the capabilities of the pilot leaders in the Dutch pilot, in addition to the presentation, a workshop was also conducted. In the workshop, participants were asked about their motivations across five different factors regarding their energy use and behaviours. The motivations highlighted by citizens are shown in Table 4.

The content for the presentation and workshop was created by the pilot leaders with assistance from WP3 leaders. The presentation and workshop were spoken in Dutch, except for the presentation on persona development which was delivered by WP3 representatives in English. The sessions were presented primarily in the local language to ensure participants could understand the topics being presented and could express themselves comfortably during the workshop. The presentation and workshop were led by the pilot partners with the support of WP3 leaders. The results of the BNO analysis are displayed in Table 3.

Based on the BNO analysis, the key focus areas which will be discussed with the Dutch pilot leaders in the checkpoint meeting include:

- The validation of persona profiles
- No need to reinvent the wheel, instead synchronise with current projects (community-led & Thermo Bello)
- Increased collaboration and knowledge flow between ACCEPT & the community
- Climate change remains at the forefront of decision making
- Participation in innovation as a collective
- Enjoyment is a factor – both in services and research/innovation
- Privacy

Figure 7. Dutch pilot partners giving a guided tour to WP3 leaders

Figure 8. ACCEPT presentation given by Dutch pilot partners and WP3 leaders

Table 3. BNO analysis of the Dutch pilot sit

Societal context	
<p>Strong sense of community with community-led projects</p> <p>Energy cooperatives have a close relationship with the community</p> <p>Communal areas within the pilot region promote responsibility and togetherness</p> <p>The community area is progressive in terms of green thinking and behaviour</p> <p>Community planning is seasonally orientated – maximising PV use in summer and in winter maximising cheap wind power</p>	
Citizens	
<u>Barriers</u>	<p>Notable concerns regarding data security,</p> <p>Concerns over the impact on thermal comfort with Dr scheme</p> <p>Some fears over how the level of control changes and the potential relinquishing of control</p>
<u>Needs</u>	<p>Various and differing needs between different types of users – personas will be important</p> <p>Ensure different gender feedback is gathered so diverse community is accounted for</p>
<u>Opportunities</u>	<p>Strong sense of community. Members volunteer for and lead community projects, including energy-related projects</p> <p>The community encouraged open debate amongst its members. Open to innovation and a good source of feedback on new solutions</p> <p>A strong relationship with Thermo Bello project</p> <p>Knowledgeable and progressive community regarding green energy behaviour and culture</p> <p>Enthusiastic and interested to participate</p>

Table 4. The output of the motivation assessment workshop with the Dutch pilot community

Climate and environment	Social	Financial	Comfort	Autonomy
Climate Sustainability/social Energy must be saved Feedback on self-consumption Environment Will there be enough power later? Proper/smarter use of energy (use when there is enough green energy)	Innovation research Building up knowledge together Initiate development Contribute and learn from each other Community building The neighbourhood must continue to innovate Curiosity Togetherness Social Concerns about resistance when people see their own energy consumption Concerns about a reduction in living comfort among housemates Fun	Save money Awareness of consumption per device so that you can conveniently switch on/off Freedom in the moment of choice of electricity demand Insight into energy consumption Maximum profit of excess energy from the solar panels	Privacy User friendly Technically easy; should be fun Worrying about hassle if we're really going to do this Not too much administration Does it work?	Organize your own house efficiently Small-scale energy supply Reverse privatization of energy supply (is not a market product) Control in use and results Regional energy self-sufficiency

3.2.4. Pilot Site Community: Arena Innovation Community & Fondazione la Sosta, Switzerland

The Swiss pilot site visit was completed over 2 days in M22. An agenda for the site visit was created after online discussions between WP3 leaders and the Swiss pilot partners. The agenda included visiting the community area in Massagno and several interviews with various stakeholders and citizens. The interviews were organised by the pilot partners, and in total five interviews were conducted. The first interview was with the chief financial officer of AEM and was conducted in English. The other interviews were with citizens and prosumers who were participants or residents in the Massagno region. The interview with the CFO of AEM provided the perspective of a business energy expert, whilst the interview with the prosumers and citizens gave the perspective of residents living in the area. Discussion guides for the interviews were created by WP3 leaders. The interviews were led by the pilot partners so topics could be discussed in the local language. The results of the BNO analysis are displayed in Table 5.

Based on the BNO analysis, the key focus areas which will be discussed with the Swiss pilot leaders in the checkpoint meeting include:

- Collective community interest in innovation aimed at climate change
- Creation of forums for discussion and awareness raising
- A need for clarity on what Demand Response is – what is controlled and what it means

- The building of trust is important
- Incorporating current business operations into ACCEPT for longevity beyond the project lifespan
- Need for increased & regular information flow & Knowledge raising
- The communal area provides an opportunity for education/awareness raising

Figure 9. Swiss pilot partners providing WP3 with a tour of the pilot region

Table 5. BNO analysis of the Swiss pilot sit

Societal context		
<p>The core is the sale of electricity; the reduction of consumption creates a rise in the electricity price to the consumers because part of the electricity price is related to a fixed cost increase.</p> <p>The current situation is characterised by a shift in paradigm; which creates opportunities. Must be progressive</p> <p>The Swiss energy market is old, changes are not industrial but political.</p> <p>In Switzerland, rich people with an old mentality, thus not so open to change.</p> <p>Strong sense of community, with many services within the communal area. Parks, schools (kindergarten, primary, high), general practitioners, supermarkets, sports centre with swimming pool.</p>		
	DSO	Citizens
<u>Barriers</u>	<p>The current flat price tariff does not incentivize demand shifting.</p> <p>A problem from the desire to install their own control / smart meter, detaching from the DSO. People lose control and AEM has no capacity to help.</p>	<p>no discussion or confrontation with neighbours about the energy community.</p> <p>lack of trust with electricity companies: one has to become a trusted advisor, not just the company asking for money for bills. Electricity distributors are generally viewed negatively because the only contact is the payment of the bill.</p> <p>Lack of information which halts participation</p> <p>A belief that industry uses the most energy and there is a lack of opportunities to save at the individual level</p> <p>On DR, people are not aware of the need and fear external control</p> <p>PV is interesting; however, it requires a very large investment: not for the technology itself, but for the renovation of the façade and roof before installation.</p>
<u>Needs</u>	<p>App for DR: it is important to transform the data into usable and understandable information</p> <p>It is useful to form alliances with other companies. The competition comes from different sectors than energy, for example, digital and communication companies.</p> <p>Giving a solution without knowing the problem does not work. You have to say that is an opportunity with them.</p>	<p>Climate change is important for nature.</p> <p>No problem with the control level if the controlling body is a trusted partner</p> <p>Willing to participate in DR but not for all appliances (e.g. happy for the heat pump but not other household appliances)</p> <p>Info should come from trusted bodies (e.g. electricity companies), using all possible communication vectors (town halls, schools, etc.) in an educational manner</p>

	<p style="text-align: center;">CONSUMER ENGAGEMENT AND DESIGN VALIDATION ROADMAP</p>	<p>Price is a strong motivator</p> <p>The community should be included in development to increase understanding and promote change</p> <p>More regular updates on the project (3/6 months with a flyer or newsletter).</p> <p>Motivated by participating in innovation; not for economic reasons</p> <p>Tangible advice is important – relatable information flow needed</p> <p>Increase knowledge – people unsure of which appliances are heavy on consumption</p>
<p><u>Opportunities</u></p>	<p>The current rising energy price is an opportunity for companies. Change in what you do: services, products, technology.</p> <p>Smart meters roll-out is mandatory before 2027, but AEM has already completed the roll-out. This gives the opportunity to know the profile of users for dispatch control and demand-side management (solar PV, heat pumps, electric vehicles, etc.)</p> <p>AEM is developing an app for their customers. Customers will be able to see their consumption (aggregated but also the profile).</p> <p>AEM is a small company with a lot of possibilities for R&D, and support for bigger companies.</p>	<p>Willing to participate in DR. willing, at the community level especially.</p> <p>app to monitor consumption would be very useful if it is part of general user education and awareness-raising</p> <p>There is a positive view of current energy-saving measures, such as motion sensors on streetlights</p> <p>already changing daily behaviours – positive outlook for DR (switching to microwave meals to reduce consumption through oven use)</p> <p>reducing consumption and emission is of high importance (reasons include security of supply – can be used as a motivation for encouraging participation in DR to provide flexibility)</p>

3.2.5. Pilot Site Community: Aspra Spitia Community, Greece

At the time of writing, the Greek pilot site visit had not yet been completed. However, some preliminary information and feedback from the Greek community were gathered by the Greek pilot partners through face-to-face interviews conducted in M20. Therefore, some preliminary output has been generated through a BNO analysis of these interviews, presented in Table 6. Before the checkpoint meetings in M26, the BNO analysis in Table 6 will be supplemented with the information gathered from the Greek pilot site visit scheduled at the end of M23.

Based on the current BNO analysis, the key focus areas which will be discussed with the Greek pilot leaders in the checkpoint meeting include:

- Regular and involving participation to maintain interest
- Promotion of safety aspects
- Interlinkage between community, industry and lifestyle
- Interest in the broader picture and EU innovation project landscape

Table 6. BNO analysis of the Greek pilot sit

Societal context	
Community is synonymous with the companies/industry – connected financially and to public sports institutions etc.	
Close proximity for residents - Don't really use cars – use bikes or walk and don't travel too far. Work is close by (5 mins by car to the industrial area)	
Strong sense of community, 3000 people in the village, majority work in same area/industry. They all know each other and spend time together in the evening or at events	
	Citizens
<u>Barriers</u>	<p>Dislike that houses are old (built in the 60s) pay a lot for renovation, no new building options</p> <p>Doors and windows are wooden so insulation is not great – summer is often hot and winter cold.</p> <p>Electrical circuits in the homes are old – so tenants make modifications, and connections can be bad due to amateur renovations</p>
<u>Needs</u>	<p>Safety was a big concern – sleeping with open windows etc, kids playing free</p> <p>Confusion about which project they were in, lack of continued interaction, the ACCEPT project had to be reintroduced and explained</p> <p>Desire to lower consumption and have a positive environmental impact – eg concerned about AC usage</p> <p>They want to reduce the cost, most do not have subsidised costs from the industry – worried about the high prices</p> <p>Prefer faster running projects from companies – ACCEPT is pretty slow</p>
<u>Opportunities</u>	<p>Some are investing in new technologies, such as heat pumps</p> <p>Interest in being part of a bigger EU project</p> <p>Community members have a good business understanding and knowledge of EU projects</p>

4. Design validation

Design validation is the second main element of the consumer engagement and design validation roadmap which focuses on gathering feedback on the ACCEPT solutions and services. This chapter will describe the persona development and user testing engagement activities plan which are integral in the design validation process.

4.1. Persona development

In software development, a lack of user involvement is often a major barrier to developing an APP or platform that a potential user needs and wants. A solution to this is utilising personas to support software developers in designing a tool that will be used and liked by the end-users (Blonkvist, 2002). User personas are research-based fictional characters, that are modelled from information gathered from real users (Korsgaard et al., 2020). Personas describe the target group's habits, motivations, needs, frustrations and challenges related to the given service. Creating user personas which provide a profile of a real person provides developers with a tangible image of an end-user around which they can build the software around. Without the information and guidance of persona research, the software can end up being developed for the so-called 'elastic user', which is the perceived user profile generated solely from a developer's perspective. Once the final user persona profiles have been created, a clearer picture of the end user's needs, concerns and motivations related to the energy system, energy behaviours and demand response will become apparent. The information provided by the personas will be a crucial component for tailoring the C-APP to real users. In addition, the persona profiles will fit with the wider WP7 and WP3 activities (e.g. C-APP testing and pilot site engagement activities) to inform the consumer engagement and design validation roadmap.

4.1.1. Literature background

A comprehensive literature search was conducted to examine which topics the questionnaire for investigating personas such be designed around. As high drop-out rates in demand response (DR) programs continue to be an obstacle to reaching DR goals, recent studies have been exploring the use of personas related to energy consumption and behaviour in demand response programmes (Olawale, Gilbert and Reyna, 2022). When looking at the variables that are most salient in demand response programs, evidence suggests the comfort of DR participants is a major cause of the failure of the program (Aghniaey et al, 2017). Measuring comfort levels is a complicated issue given the fact that the perception of comfort is dependent on subjective human perception, rather than a quantifiable variable (Olawale, Gilber and Reyna, 2022). Thus, for the creation of user personas that focus on comfort, and everyday routines a comprehensive mixed method of qualitative and quantitative research will be implemented to assess personas.

4.1.2. Questionnaire design

Combining learnings from the literature search with some preliminary information gathered from the pilot site visits (see chapter 3), a questionnaire was created to investigate persona profiles within the ACCEPT pilot communities. The questionnaire was created in English and translated with the help of the pilot partners into the language of each pilot site. For the structure of the questionnaire, a mixed methodology was utilised to combine quantitative data analysis with more complex insights gathered through qualitative analyses, allowing the creation of a highly descriptive and comprehensive user profile (Jansen et al., 2022). For the quantitative section of the questionnaire, a mix of multiple choice and Likert scale questions was used to investigate social and psychological factors related to energy behaviour. The factors investigated and the corresponding questions are shown in Table 7.

In addition to the quantitative questions, two qualitative questions focussing on everyday comfort and motivation towards energy saving were included. These two questions will be crucial in determining how and why an end-user will be willing and motivated to use the C-APP and what would they like to see on the interface. Other questions were also included related to the propensity for participation in DR and the demographics of users (for the full persona development questionnaire, see Appendix A).

Table 7. Questions and corresponding categories used for the quantitative section of the persona development questionnaire

	Interest	Knowledge	Technology	Political	Social	Financial
<u>Questions</u>	I think about the environment when using energy	I am always looking for ways to reduce my energy bills	I am interested in trying new technologies	My political attitudes are irrelevant when it comes to my energy consumption behaviour	I would like my friends and neighbours to know that I am taking action in terms of saving energy and protecting the environment	The rising price of energy is my primary motivator to be more mindful about my energy consumption
	I am interested in making my home more environmentally friendly	I want to learn about my household's electricity usage	I always try to buy new technological equipment for my home	My views on climate change are in line with my political opinions	I think everyone should "do their bit" for the environment	My energy bills are of big concern for me
	I think it is important to know how much energy I am using	I don't know what I can do to save energy in my home	I am interested in smart home technologies	I think climate change is a political matter for many people	I don't believe my individual contribution will help fight climate change	My energy consumption behaviour largely depends on how much money I can save by being more mindful

4.1.3. Analysis

A principal component analysis will be performed on the quantitative data to identify groupings of traits from the factors shown in Table 7. The quantitative analysis will be combined with the data gathered from the qualitative questions to formulate various persona profiles. An example of a persona profile is shown in Figure 10. A more in-depth description of the analyses will be presented with the results in Deliverable D7.2.

Figure 10. Example of a persona profile

4.1.4. Timeline and current stage

The timeline of the tasks required for the persona development process is shown in Figure 11. Following the initial literature review conducted in M22, the questionnaire was shared with the pilot partners so they could provide their feedback and support with the translation process. Following this, the finalised questionnaire was distributed amongst the pilot site communities in M22 by the pilot partners via an online link. The questionnaire is currently still being circulated and is scheduled to be closed in M23, giving participants one month to submit their responses. The analysis will be carried out in M24. The final persona profiles can be expected by the end of M25 (January 2023).

Figure 11. Persona development timeline

4.2. User testing roadmap

To ensure a user-centric approach is undertaken regarding the development of the C-APP, user testing sessions will take place with the consortium partners and community members within the four pilot sites. External user testing with the community members forms a critical component in the methodology for the C-APP development. The user testing process puts early versions of the APP in the hands of citizens so they can provide feedback to guide the technical development. This feedback includes citizen's perspectives on the design and functions of the C-APP. Gathering feedback from actual end users is essential for creating an APP that users want and need. In addition to gathering feedback from external end users, it is also prudent to consult ACCEPT consortium members. Therefore, the user testing methodology utilised in ACCEPT included both internal and external user testing. This methodology is shown in Figure 12 and explained in detail below.

Figure 12. Citizen APP development methodology

As shown in Figure 12, the C-APP development breaks down into 4 stages. The first 2 stages aim to gather feedback at the internal level (from the consortium partners) and the latter 2 stages aim to gather feedback from external entities, primarily end users.

4.2.1. Feedback from technical partners

In M15, the C-APP was presented to technical partners by the lead developers in WP5. In this session, the C-APP was presented in the form of mockup images, with the functionality and navigation explained in the presentation by the lead technical development team. Feedback was gathered from other technical partners in the form of an open discussion. The goal was to gather opinions and perspectives from other technical experts to improve the design of the C-APP before gathering feedback from external users.

4.2.2. Feedback from pilot partners

In M18, following some adjustments to the C-APP based on the feedback gathered from the technical partners, the same mock-ups and process was used for gathering feedback from the pilot partners. The pilot partners were consulted as they can provide insight based on knowledge of their local regions, communities and users.

4.2.3. Feedback from pilot site users: Round 1

In M23-24, following the internal user testing sessions, interviews and workshops will be held to gather feedback from the end users in each pilot site. Due to the importance of the external feedback, and to ensure that all partners responsible for the gathering of external feedback were aligned and understood what was required of them, an external user testing planning timeline was created (Figure 13).

Figure 13. External user testing planning timeline

The external testing planning timeline is broken down into 6 phases:

1. **Goal definition:** Discuss with all partners the goals of the user testing session to determine precisely what kind of feedback was required from the external user testing sessions. It was decided that the sessions revolved around 2 main objectives:
 - Design
 - Layout, colour, and style preferences
 - Navigational ease
 - Function
 - Determine if the current functions are useful
 - Identify missing functions
 - Identify the most valuable functions
2. **Methodology confirmation:** Defining how the feedback would be gathered. The technical team confirmed a URL which links participants to a live version of the C-APP (with dummy data) would be ready by M23. Therefore, all pilot sites confirmed they would use this live version via the link
3. **User identification:** Pilot sites needed to identify potential users within their community who could be contacted and offered the opportunity to take part in the user feedback session. It was agreed that the pilot partners would first familiarise themselves with the C-APP and receive training on how to run the sessions before contacting potential participants.
4. **Material preparation:** Preparing the required supplementary material which would allow pilot partners to moderate the user testing sessions. The material required included a consent form, briefing document, guidance notes, discussion guide and SUS questionnaire (all testing materials are available in Appendices B-F). This deliverable focuses on outlining the plans for the engagements, further details on the materials, such as the SUS questionnaires purpose and function, will be outlined in D7.2 which focuses specifically on the results of the consumer validation of the ACCEPT solutions and services, including the user testing.
5. **User testing sessions:** Pilot partners conducted user testing sessions with the end users. It was advised the user testing would be one-to-one sessions held by the pilot partners with end users from the pilot region. The sessions would take 60 minutes and be conducted remotely via Teams, or a similar platform which permitted screen sharing.
6. **Feedback analysis:** After completing the user testing sessions, pilot partners will send the feedback, in the form of notes and the SUS questionnaires, to WP3 leaders. The feedback will then be consolidated and analysed so it can then be shared with consortium partners and then passed on to the technical team for them to develop or re-design the C-APP based on the feedback received.

At the time of writing, the external user testing was in stage 5, with pilot partners organising testing sessions with community end users. The results of these sessions will be reported in D7.2.

4.2.4. Feedback from pilot site users: Round 2

Following the first round of gathering external feedback, it is important to create feedback loops by implementing multiple rounds of external end-user testing. This allows for the end user to not only see improvements as the C-APP develops throughout the project lifespan but also gives users a chance to provide further input and play an integral role in the APP's development. Furthermore, having several dedicated user testing sessions ensures that stringent user validation takes place and a better-quality product is developed. At this stage, the specific details of the second round of testing are not yet defined. Deciding when and how to implement follow-up external rounds of testing is best decided after analysing the first round of external user testing results and also considering project development and the pilot-specific engagement roadmaps.

5. Conclusion

Following on from the work outlined in the previous version of this deliverable (D3.7), an updated and comprehensive consumer engagement and design validation roadmap has been created. Although flexibility is required when planning and carrying out engagement activities in a project spanning 42 months, many concrete engagements have been determined. The planned engagements cover the consumer engagements in each pilot site and the design validation activities related to the development of the ACCEPT tools and services. Following the in-person pilot site visits, information has been gathered which will allow for the planning of pilot-specific engagement roadmaps that accommodate the needs of the citizens and stakeholders within each pilot site and also align with the goals of the ACCEPT project. Regarding the engagement activities associated with the tools and services, a clear and precise plan has been created for the development of personas and the user testing of the C-APP.

The generation of the pilot-specific roadmaps is somewhat delayed due to the inability to carry out site visits until M21. However, 3 of the 4 site visits have been completed and the final site visit is scheduled for the end of M23. A thorough analysis has been completed for each pilot community through the BNO model. The output from this analysis has provided key focus areas to discuss during the checkpoint meetings scheduled for M26 with the pilot partners. Combining the output from the BNO analysis with the information from the general consumer engagement and design validation roadmap presented in this deliverable will allow for the production of the pilot-specific engagement roadmaps.

6. References

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7. Appendix

7.1. Appendix A: Persona development questionnaire

Persona Questionnaire

As part of the ACCEPT project, we invite you to fill in this questionnaire in order to get a better view on how to best develop the ACCEPT application with the users in mind. We would like to make sure we understand your motivations and frustrations when it comes to day-to-day energy use. The output of this questionnaire will be the so-called user personas, which will help the software developers to design the applications in line with your needs and preferences.

Please feel free to be answer honestly, as the questionnaire is completely anonymus. You can decide to withdraw from participation at any time.

Completing the questionnaire should take around 10 minutes.

Open ended questions

In this section, we would like to know about your everyday habits and your personal experiences and opinions about energy consumption. Please express yourself with your own words, and share anything that you think relates to the question!

1. When thinking about your average daily routine at home, what comforts can or * can't you compromise on (e.g. cooking, washing, shower, temperature, etc.)?
2. Do you think it is important to be mindful about energy consumption? If so, why? * If not, why not?

Lifestyle

3. How often do you work/study from home? *
 - Every day
 - Couple of days a week
 - Majority of the week
 - Never
4. How often do you cook at home? *
 - Multiple times a day
 - Every day
 - Couple of times a week
 - Once a week
 - Less than once a week
5. Which of these household appliances are present in your household? Please * select all that apply.
 - Water boiler
 - Electric coffee maker
 - Air conditioner
 - Sauna
 - Pool pump
 - Electric vehicle (car, motorbike, scooter, etc.)
 - Washing machine
 - Dishwasher
 - Dryer
 - Smart home system

Energy knowledge

Not at all knowledgeable - Very knowledgeable on a scale of 1-4

6. Which appliances in your home consume the most energy? *

7. How many kilowatts your home consumes each month? *
8. Where your energy comes from? *
9. The options that are available for making your home more energy efficient? *

Motivation towards renewable energy usage

10. What appeals to you most about using renewable energy to power your home? *
Choose maximum 3!

Saving money
 Increased comfort (e.g. temperature control)
 Fighting climate change
 Preserving natural resources
 Providing a good example to others
 Generating my own energy
 Optimising my energy consumption/using energy more efficiently
 Generating profit on the energy I use
 Sharing energy with others
 Other

11. If you chose "other" in the previous question, please specify:
12. What concerns you the most about using renewable energy to power your home? Choose maximum 3! *

Higher prices
 Safety issues
 The reliability of my energy supply
 Reduced comfort levels
 Uncertainty about where my energy is coming from
 It would require time thinking about energy use
 I don't know enough about renewable energy Using technology
 I don't understand
 Other

13. If you chose "other" in the previous question, please specify:

Attitudes towards energy consumption

Strongly agree – Strongly disagree on a scale of 1-6

14. I think about the environment when using energy. *
15. I am always looking for ways to reduce my energy bills. *
Strongly agree
16. I am interested in smart technologies. *
17. I think it is important to know how much energy I am using. *
18. My energy consumption behaviour largely depends on how much money I can save by being more mindful. *
19. I want to learn about my household's electricity usage. *
20. I think climate change is a political matter for many people. *

21. I am interested in trying new technologies. *
22. I would feel safer if I could rely on locally produced energy sources. *
23. I don't believe my individual contribution will help fight climate change. *
24. The rising price of energy is my primary motivator to be more mindful about my * energy consumption.
25. I always try to buy new technological equipment for my home. *
26. I would like my friends and neighbours to know that I am taking action in terms * of saving energy and protecting the environment.
27. I am interested in making my home more environmentally friendly. *
28. My energy bills are of big concern for me. *
29. My political attitudes are irrelevant when it comes to my energy consumption * behaviour.
30. I don't know what I can do to save energy in my home. *
31. I don't mind being dependent on big energy providers. *
32. My views on climate change are in line with my political opinions. *
33. I want to be completely self-reliant in my energy production and consumption. *
34. I think everyone should "do their bit" for the environment. *

Demographic data

35. Country of residence *

Greece
Spain
The Netherlands
Switzerland

36. What kind of settlement do you live in? *

Capital city
Bigger city
Town
Village

37. Gender *

Male
Female
Prefer not to say

38. Age range *

18-25 years old
26-35 years old
36-45 years old
46-55 years old

56-65 years old
66+ years old

39. How would you describe your marital status? *

Married/live with partner
Divorced/widowed
Single
Prefer not to say

40. What is the number of adults (18-65) living in your home? *

0
1
2
3
4
5 or more

41. What is the number of seniors (65 +) living in your home? *

0
1
2
3
4
5 or more

42. What is the number of children or teenagers (under 18) living in your home? *

0
1
2
3
4
5 or more

43. What is your educational background? *

Primary school
Secondary/High education
Vocational School
Bachelor's Degree
Master's Degree
Doctoral or higher degree

44. Current occupational situation *

Paid employed
Self employed / Entrepreneur
Unpaid work
Seeking employment
Retired/pensioned
Full-time student
Unable to work
Stay at home parent
Prefer not to say

45. How would you describe your (last) occupation? *

Farmer
 Entrepreneur
 Top manager
 Middle manager
 High education employee
 Clerk
 Skilled worker
 Unskilled worker
 Other (customer visiting, travelling, teleworking, etc.)
 Full-time student
 Never had a job

46. Exact job title (if employed)

47. How would you describe your household income, in comparison to your country average? *

Much higher
 A bit higher
 Similar to average
 A bit lower
 Much lower
 Prefer not to say

48. Ethnicity *

I am part of an ethnic minority
 I am part of an ethnic majority
 I prefer not to say

7.2. Appendix B: User testing consent form

Participant Consent Form

I _____ (Print Name) agree to participate in the ACCEPT project.

- The purpose and nature of the study have been explained to me verbally/in writing.
- I confirm that I am over 18 years of age and that I am participating voluntarily.
- I understand that I can withdraw from the study, without repercussions, at any time, whether before it starts or while I am participating.
- I understand that data provided to the project will be treated confidentially and that my anonymity will be ensured in any post-testing reports based on the information/feedback I provide.
- I understand that any information/extracts I provide during the user testing session may be used/quoted in any subsequent publications.

Initials:

Date:

7.3. Appendix C: User testing briefing document

Participant Briefing Document

Project Overview: at the centre of the ACCEPT H2020 project is the concept of “energy communities” with the collective approach to bring citizens, local businesses, and organizations together to produce and consume locally generated renewable energy. The EU-funded project intends to develop and deliver a digital toolbox that offers innovative digital services to energy communities to help reduce their dependency on fossil fuels. Key to this is saving energy in the users’ households and thus be able to reduce their electricity bill without compromising their quality of life, but instead improve the level of comfort in their homes through smart devices. In ACCEPT, these developed tools will be demonstrated and validated in four pilot sites in Greece, the Netherlands, Spain and Switzerland involving more than 3,000 people and 750 residences.

Potential involvement: As part of the ACCEPT project, a citizen APP is being developed which will help citizens to monitor their energy use and cost as well as facilitate active participation in energy saving events. This citizen APP is being developed with a user-centred approach, which means the design and functions of the APP are being developed *with* rather than for the user. This user testing session today will allow us to gather insight from you, the user, and improve the APP based on the feedback you provide.

What does it mean for me?

- Participation in the study is entirely voluntary and nobody ‘has to take part’. Participants should be over 18 years of age.
- Contributions will be anonymised if this is participants’ wish.
- Participants retain the right to withdraw from the study at any time in the process.
 - where data can be linked to a specific participant, participants can withdraw consent at any time during and up to two weeks after the collection of the data – in which case the material will be deleted;
 - where data has been gathered collectively (*e.g.*, focus groups) participants can withdraw any time, but the data collected up to that point will be retained;
 - where data has been gathered anonymously participants can withdraw any time until the data is collected by the researchers.
- Data collected will be used only for this project and potential follow-up studies. It will be stored securely and not made available to anybody outside of the research team. Security will include: password protection of audio and video recordings; encryption of laptops; non-use of USB memory keys; and use of secure network file storage for long-term storage.
- Any physical documents will be stored in locked cabinets in the offices of the research team. The data will be securely stored for a period of ten years before disposal.

For more information on the project, please check the project website: <https://www.accept-project.eu/>

7.4. Appendix D: User testing guidance notes

ACCEPT APP User testing

Guidance notes

Objectives

Collect feedback from users regarding:

- Design
 - Layout, colour, and style preferences
 - Navigational ease
- Function
 - Determine if the current functions are useful
 - Identify missing functions
 - Identify the most valuable functions

Audience

- 12-20 residential end users
 - Spain: n=3-5
 - Greece: n=3-5
 - Switzerland: n=3-5
 - Netherlands: n=3-5
- Demographically diversity should be prioritized (e.g. gender, age)

Methodology

- Moderated (local language) 1x1 interviews
 - To be moderated by local pilot partner
 - A second note-taker is strongly recommended
- To be held remotely using Microsoft Teams (in-person also ok)
- 45-60 minutes in length
- Incentive if required (e.g. €50 gift card)
 - Interest seems to be high based on pilot feedback – but incentives can be considered if unable to find users
- “User Council”
 - Participants should be offered the chance to be part of the “user council” in which the same users from a pilot can be contacted at a later date for further feedback

Things to know about the APP as the tester:

- Don't look at the EV charging tab as there isn't currently a plan to include this
- Only the 'notifications' section will be in the settings tab, 'comfort zone' will not be included – so no need to discuss this section with the user

Things to advise participants of before testing:

- That its ok to bypass the warning when opening the log in page on their browser – reassure them it is safe & assist them to navigate
- Don't click on the “more details” link on any page as it leads to an error page
- Consumption per device graphs on this first version of the APP will not be in the actual version – therefore, advise participants that in the future final version:
 - Graphs will not be based on data but may be suggestive
 - Topology graph will be less detailed

7.5. Appendix E: User testing discussion guide

ACCEPT APP User testing

Discussion guide

Introduction and consent (5 min)

- Introduce yourself and the note-taker
- Info sheet giving brief description of ACCEPT project and user testing session can be used

Prototype introduction (5 min)

- This should be a brief introduction to the app (take no longer than 5 minutes!)
- Be sure to inform the participant about the prototype limitations. (See "Things to advise participants of before testing" section of guidance sheet)

Tasks (4-5 with debrief) (15-30 min)

- Check the upcoming requests for the DR events
- Check your participation rate in DR events
- What was today's total energy consumption and today's forecasted total energy consumption
- What is the energy consumption and cost of your lighting and oven appliances
- In the analytics tab, get the graph to only show 'price'

After each task, have a short debrief

- How easy/difficult was the task?
- Did it meet expectations?
- What did they like?
- What could be improved?

General feedback (10 min)

- General impressions
- Surprises/alignment with expectations
- Layout appeal
- Navigational ease
- Most useful functions
- Least useful functions
- Missing functions
- Mobile link..

Building the FAQs (5 mins)

- Let the user ask questions – this is not for you to answer, just to write down so these can be included in the FAQ section of the APP

Extra questions of interest - if time available (2 minutes)

- Did they understand the colour coding on the dashboard related to comfort levels?
- Does the home dashboard have the right quick-look info? Would they prefer to see other elements on the home screen?
- Is the left tool bar clear enough for them to navigate?

System Usability Scale (SUS) (5 min)

- Go to the System Usability Scale word document and ask all 10 questions - Ask participant to provide verbal response and type answer in
- Remember to choose 'save as' function after completion when saving the SUS word file so as not to over-write the template
- Note: this is an assessment specified in the GA so be sure to complete the SUS

Wrap up (2 min)

- Final comments
- Invitation/Reminder for "User Council" participation – if they agree take their email address

- Thank the participant

7.6. Appendix F: System Usability Scale

ACCEPT APP User testing

System Usability Scale

System Usability Scale (SUS) (5 min)

Ask the participant to provide a response on a scale of 1 – 5.

1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neither, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree.

Type the number of their response next to each question.

- I think that I would like to use this system frequently.
- I found the system unnecessarily complex.
- I thought the system was easy to use.
- I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.
- I found the various functions in this system were well integrated
- I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.
- I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly
- I found the system very cumbersome to use.
- I felt very confident using the system.
- I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.

Remember to 'save as' so as not to over-write the template.